

Start to do VS Start doing

A Diachronic Corpus-based Analysis

Introduction

This paper aims to analyze the occurrence of the constructions “Start to + V.inf” and “Start + V.ing” as in “start to do” and “start doing” through time. To better see the change through time, the Corpus of Historical American English (COHA), which contains the language data from 1810 to 2010, is chosen. The corpus has a total number of 385 million words collected from 115,000 texts, and each decade has roughly the same balance of data from fiction, popular magazine, newspaper, and non-fiction books.

Methods

The regular expressions used to extract and filter the data are as follow:

- [start].[v*] to _v?i
The first regular expression matches “start” as a verb in any form, namely started, starts, and starting followed by “to” and any “infinitive verb”.
- [start].[v*] _v?g
The second regular expression matches “start” as a verb in any form, namely started, starts, and starting followed by any “verb with -ing ending”.

Results

Choosing “Chart” above the search box with the regular expressions, the result of the frequency in each decade is illustrated in a table with bar charts. The bar charts represent a normalized frequency or a proportion of an occurrence per million words which is calculated by comparing the frequency of an occurrence with the size of a corpus in a particular decade that the frequency is counted. This prevents a raw frequency from being misinterpreted because a word may seem to occur significantly more often, but that is only because there are more words in a corpus. Below are the result tables of “Start to + V.inf” and “Start + V.ing”.

- Start to + V.inf

SECTION	ALL	1820	1830	1840	1850	1860	1870	1880	1890	1900	1910	1920	1930	1940	1950	1960	1970	1980	1990	2000	2010
FREQ	26643	5	26	36	37	68	101	210	267	510	810	1507	1690	1963	2162	2010	2159	2551	3417	3624	3490
WORDS (M)	405	7.0	13.7	15.8	16.5	16.9	18.8	20.1	20.4	22.0	23.1	25.7	27.7	27.4	28.7	29.1	28.8	29.9	33.1	34.8	35.5
PER MIL	65.79	0.72	1.90	2.28	2.24	4.01	5.38	10.46	13.07	23.21	35.06	58.64	60.99	71.64	75.43	69.02	74.89	85.46	103.08	104.07	98.44

- Start + V.ing

SECTION	ALL	1820	1830	1840	1850	1860	1870	1880	1890	1900	1910	1920	1930	1940	1950	1960	1970	1980	1990	2000	2010
FREQ	29918	0	0	3	1	2	1	3	16	30	163	441	1408	1843	2298	2544	2847	2965	4546	5349	5458
WORDS (M)	405	7.0	13.7	15.8	16.5	16.9	18.8	20.1	20.4	22.0	23.1	25.7	27.7	27.4	28.7	29.1	28.8	29.9	33.1	34.8	35.5
PER MIL	73.87	0.00	0.00	0.19	0.06	0.12	0.05	0.15	0.78	1.37	7.06	17.16	50.82	67.26	80.18	87.35	98.75	99.32	137.14	153.61	153.95

The constructions “Start to + V.inf” and “Start + V.ing” occur more frequently during the past 200 years. The construction “Start to + V.inf” was used only sparingly in the 19th century, though it was found more often in the latter half of the century from 5 to 23 words per million, and it continued to increase in the following decades. The construction “Start + V.ing”, on the other hand, was rarely used in the 19th century with the proportion of the frequency of only around 1 word per million.

In the 20th century between 1910 and 1930, the proportion of the frequency of “Start to + V.inf” and “Start + V.ing” increased significantly from 35 to 60 and 7 to 50 words per million respectively. Then, in the following 40 years during 1970 - 2000, there was a dramatic rise again from 74 to 104 and 98 to 153 words per million consecutively. It is interesting that although “Start + V.ing” saw a much lower occurrence than “Start to + V.inf” in the beginning, its use skyrocketed to nearly the same level with “Start to + V.inf” in 1930 - 1940 (50 and 60, 67 and 71), and its frequency finally surpassed “Start to + V.inf” in 1950 (80 and 75). In the following decades until 2010, the occurrence of “Start + V.ing” continued to outnumber the one of its counterpart.

Towards the beginning of the 21st century, both constructions seemed to reach a plateau where their occurrence was stagnant. From 1990 to 2010, the proportion of the frequency of the two constructions changed only 6 words per million for “Start to + V.inf” and 16 for “Start + V.ing”. The construction “Start to + V.inf” which was previously outnumbered by its counterpart even fell slightly from 104 to 98 words per million.

Summary and Discussion

All in all, throughout the timespan of the past 2 centuries, the constructions “Start to + V.inf” and “Start + V.ing” saw a trend in accordance with the S-curve model where only the slight number is found in the beginning, starts to rise in the middle, and reaches a plateau towards the end. This trend also reflects conventionality by diffusion. The constructions started out very low but became more popular as it diffused or, in other words, when more people started to acquire it. At the end of the process, it was conventionalized, and the diffusion stopped. The occurrence stayed steady. I believe the reason why “start doing” has become more popular than “start to do” is due to phonological as well as morphosyntax factors. Obviously, “start doing” is easier to pronounce than “start to do”. For example, the most frequent phrases are “started talking” and “started walking” at 615 and 445 times respectively compared to “started to say” and “started to get” at a lower hits of 564 and 442 times respectively. In addition, viewing from the perspective of efficiency, “start doing” is more efficient or economical than “start to do” in that it has 1 less morpheme but can convey the same meaning. It would be interesting for future study to find out which kind of diffusion the two constructions have. To do this, more information is needed to be analyzed, especially the location.